

Analysis of deforestation and CO₂ emissions in Indigenous Territories of the Brazilian Amazon

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Summary

Utilising deforestation data from MapBiomass in conjunction with legacy carbon data, analysis has been carried out to determine the relationships and dynamics of deforestation and CO₂ emissions across Indigenous Territories (ITs) within the Brazilian Amazon rainforest from 1986 - 2021. Results demonstrate the link between environmental policies, their implementation and prioritisation on the rates and extent changes in deforestation within ITs. A further understanding of the introduction of Protected Areas (PAs) and ITs and this affect on the extent of deforestation and carbon dynamics across the studied timeline is also discussed.

KEYWORDS: Amazon Rainforest; Deforestation; Carbon Dynamic; Indigenous Territories.

1. Introduction

Deforestation and forest degradation in the Brazilian Amazon rainforest have increased intensely in the last decade, resulting in an increase of CO₂ emissions that have drastically affected climate change on a global scale (Matricardi, 2020; Qin et al., 2021; Jiang et al., 2023). Although this destruction can be observed across the rainforest, this paper focuses its attention on indigenous territories (ITs) and how these areas can help in mitigating deforestation and resulting CO₂ emissions across the rainforest but only if environmental policies are enforced and the borders of the territories are truly protected.

Conservation and preservation of the rainforest is paramount in mitigating climate change, protecting biodiversity and mitigating the release of terrestrial carbon whereby tropical rainforests store ~55% of this globally (Sze et al., 2021) (; Gibson et al., 2013) (; Pan et al., 2011). Deforestation within ITs of the Brazilian Amazon has seen a 129% increase from 2013 – 2021 (Silva-Junior et al., 2023).

The introduction of indigenous territories (ITs) resulted in a reduction of deforestation and demonstrated the role that protected areas could have in forest conservation in the Amazon. Being protected areas, ITs hold the capacity to act as a carbon sinks due to lower rates of deforestation and degradation within their borders. At the most part, photosynthesis is carried out at natural rates free from the impact of anthropogenic fires, illegal mining and logging, this allows for carbon sequestration contributing to climate change mitigation (Veit, Gibbs and Reytar, 2023).

2019 saw the beginning of a government term that paid no attention to the environmental implications of their purely market focused agenda, this paved the way for increased rates and areas of deforestation and illegal activities into indigenous territories (Menezes and Barbosa, 2021). Silva-Junior et al. (2023) also highlights the correlaion between deforestation in ITs and the decrease in protection. Both these

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points show a need for reinforced environmental conservation policies.

Our research looks at the dynamics of deforestation, and CO₂ emissions within ITs between 1986 – 2021 and their part in mitigating climate change by analysing their ability to reduce deforestation and CO₂ emissions within their borders. The separate periods of government terms within this timeline and their ability to implement and maintain environmental policies will also be scrutinised.

1.1. Methods

Land cover data was obtained from MapBiomas (MapBiomas., 2024). Google Earth Engine (GEE) was then used to extract the CO₂ emissions and deforested area datasets. The volume of CO₂ emissions was calculated utilising the carbon stock legacy from the former vegetation as documented in the Third National Inventory of Greenhouse Gases in Brazil. The total carbon stocks were extracted from areas where deforestation occurred in each year, this area was then multiplied by the carbon stocks present in that polygon, and then the result was further multiplied by 3.667 (the factor used to convert carbon stocks to CO₂ equivalent). Polygon data holding information regarding IT and state area boundaries sourced from Global Forest Watch was also included in this process.

During the analysis, the Mann-Kendal test (Kendall, 1938) and rates of change calculation were used as well as summing up totals of the data. The Mann-Kendal test is a non-parametric test that is used to analyse the data and distinguish whether the data has a significant monotonic upward or downward trend, the strength and direction of these trends are determined by the resulting tau values. The test was carried out in R-studio and results joined to the relevant polygon area in QGIS.

Excel was used to calculate the sum of CO₂ emissions and deforested area as well as calculating their rates of change during each government period. The overall study period of 1986 – 2021 was split into the different periods whereby different political parties were in office, the difference in their rates of change and monotonic trends could then also be interrogated.

1.2 Results and Discussion

The fluctuations of deforestation and CO₂ within ITs are displayed clearly in figure 2, the changes in these variables can be paired with their rates in figure 3 to better understand their impact. From 1995 – 2002 there seems to be a large increase in deforestation and CO₂ emissions (1995 – 1998) before the values start to decline however, figure 3 shows us that the rates of change, although positive, are very low toward 0. Whereas 2017 – 2018 shows quick fluctuations throughout the 2 years (Figure 2) and the rates of change (Figure 3) are the highest in the study period before 2021. Table 1 also shows that from 1995 – 2002, 59% of ITs display significant downward trends for deforestation.

When displayed in a geospatial format (Figure 1), the strength of the trend determined by their tau value for each IT area and can be directly compared to the trend of their neighbour. Seeing this pattern in a geographical capacity highlights that the state areas that have a stronger monotonic upward trend tend to surround IT areas that also display positive upward trends, this shows evidence of relationships between activity within state areas and that of neighbouring ITs.

The cooperation of the government in office and their willingness to enforce environmental protection policies plays a key role in the changing rate and extent of deforestation within ITs and in turn the volume of CO₂ emissions held in the immediate atmosphere (Figure 3). Figure 2 has revealed the effects of a pro-environmental government (Hochstetler, 2017), during 2003 – 2011 where the Worker's Party (PT) are in office both deforested areas and volume of CO₂ emissions are seen to decrease within ITs. The relating rates of deforestation for this period shown in figure 3 are also negative, showing a period of slower deforestation progression. To counteract this, 2021 shows extreme values of deforestation and volumes of CO₂ emissions (Figure 2) as a government with a complete disregard to environmental protection progresses with its market growth manifestos

(Menezes and Barbosa, 2021) and creates the fastest rates of deforestation and CO₂ production during the whole study period (figure 3).

Due to the known implications of increased CO₂ emissions as a greenhouse gas and the high levels of CO₂ emissions resulting from deforestation, it can be said that the willingness of the Brazilian government to enforce environmental protection policies has direct climate change implications. The fluctuations and high percent of upward trends of deforestation displayed in the data shows that regardless of the introduction of protected areas and ITs, it is the implementation and prioritisation of the environmental policies that truly protects the borders of ITs and hence helps mitigate changes to the climate.

2. Figures, Tables and Equations,

Table 1 Percentage of significant ITs that show monotonic upwards and downward trends for deforestation and CO2 emissions within each government term. NS – Nonsignificant.

Deforestation								
	1986 -1990	1991 – 1992	1993 – 1994	1995 – 2002	2003 – 2010	2011 – 2016	2017 – 2018	2019 - 2021
Percent upward trend	48.5%	NS	NS	41%	49%	55.1%	NS	75.8%
Percent downward trend	51.5%	NS	NS	59%	51%	44.9%	NS	24.2%
CO2 Emissions								
Percent upward trend	50.5%	NS	NS	42.1%	48.5%	56.8%	NS	75.6%
Percent downward trend	49.5%	NS	NS	57.9%	51.5%	43.2%	NS	24.4%

Figure 1 Maps to display the MK trend and associated tau values of deforestation for ITs and state areas across the Brazilian Amazon (a) forest (b) non-forest.

Figure 2 Deforested area and carbon emission changes within indigenous territories from 1986 - 2021 with highlighted presidency terms. The governing parties displayed include Party of the Brazilian Democratic Movement (PMDB), National Reconstruction Party (PRN), Brazilian Social Democracy Party (PSDB), Worker’s Party (PT) and Liberal Party (PL).

Figure 3 Graphs showing the rate of change in CO₂ emissions and deforested area for each government term within ITs

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Biographies

Kate A. Booth – a GIS analyst and post-graduate researcher focusing on the use of GIS and Remote

Sensing to monitor deforestation in the Brazilian Amazon. Has a bachelor's degree in Ocean Exploration from the University of Plymouth, here she discovered the world of GIS and went on to study an MSc in GIS at the University of Manchester. After a year in industry she decided to take on the part-time role of post-graduate researcher at the University of Manchester.

Celso H. L. Silva-Junior - an Environmental Engineer with a Master's and Ph.D. in Remote Sensing from Brazil's INPE, has extensive experience in geoprocessing and remote sensing. He taught at UEMA and conducted field research in the Amazon and Cerrado, specializing in forest inventories and fire mapping. He was a postdoctoral researcher at UCLA and affiliated with JPL/NASA in the USA. Currently, he's a researcher at IPAM and a professor at UFMA, focusing on land use dynamics, tropical ecosystem fires, environmental changes in the tropics, the carbon cycle, and vegetation remote sensing.

Jonathan J. Huck - a Senior Lecturer in Geographical Information Science in the Department of Geography at the University of Manchester. He has a BSc with First Class Honours in Geography from the Lancaster University, a MSc with Distinction in Geographical Information Systems from the University of Leeds, and a PhD in Geographical Information Science from Lancaster University. Jonny is a specialist in computational geography. His research focuses upon the application of GIS technologies to a range of applications including global health, the environment and segregation. He also has a long standing interest in the representation of vague geographical entities in GIS, and in understanding behavioural patterns through geographical simulation and modelling. He maintains the freely available Map-Me PGIS platform and the Shed Earth web tool for dating granite exposure. Prior to moving to academia, Jonny was the Technical Manager of a UK Wind Farm developer. He continues to operate his GIS consultancy Lune Geographic. Jonny was honoured with a fellowship of Furness College at Lancaster University in 2016 and an honorary Chair in Geographical Information Science at Gulu University, Uganda in 2019. Jonny is Chair of the Mapping, Computing and GIScience Research Group, Chair of the Mapping and GIS Innovation Group, and GIS Lead for the interdisciplinary Digital Humanities group at the University of Manchester. He is the Chair of the GIS Research UK (GISRUK) National Steering Committee, having previously chaired the 25th GISRUK Conference, held in 2017 at The University of Manchester. He has been awarded three prestigious Making a Difference Awards from the University of Manchester, including for his Community Mapping Uganda project.

Polyanna da Conceição Bispo - a Senior Lecturer in Physical Geography at the University of Manchester. She is a biologist with an MSc and PhD in remote sensing from the National Institute for Space Research (INPE), Brazil. Her research encompasses Forest Ecology and Earth Observation, contributing to the development of methodologies and strategies to monitor tropical forests, as well as understanding how environmental factors influence and shape biodiversity and forest structure. She also seeks to understand how disturbances affect the forests and how they recover after these events. Her work is also connected with climate change issues and decision-making policies.